

Psychological Determinants of Occupational Aspiration Among Students with Disabilities in Integrated Secondary Schools in Southwest, Nigeria

AUTHOR(S): OKE, CHIGOZIE CELESTINA

Abstract

This study investigated psychological determinants of occupational aspiration among students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population consisted of all 1,106 students with disabilities in integrated public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 349 students with disabilities from 12 integrated public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure. An instrument tagged "Psychological Determinants and Occupational Aspiration Questionnaire (PDOAQ)" was used to collect relevant data for the study from the respondents. The face and content validity of the instruments were determined by Guidance and Counselling experts and experts in Tests and Measurement. The instrument was said to have facial relevance and concerned with the subject matter, they claimed to measure. The reliability of the instrument was determined through test re-test method. A coefficient of 0.81 was gotten and this was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable and useful for the study. The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics, while the hypotheses postulated were subjected to inferential statistics of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that decision-making ability and self-concept are related to occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools. It was recommended among others that parents in

IJARBAS

Accepted 10 June 2021
Published 22 June 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5014810

collaboration with school management should make available necessary support that could aid students with disabilities in making the right decision about occupational aspiration.

Keywords: Psychological Determinants, Occupational Aspiration, Disabilities,

About Author

Author(s):

OKE, CHIGOZIE CELESTINA

Department of Guidance and Counselling,
Faculty of Education,
Federal University, Oye - Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Education is an indispensable tool for the development of an individual and the society at large. It is universally recognized as an instrument which is capable of providing solution to socio-economic problem when properly utilised. Olamide and Olawaye (2013) reported that both nations and individuals look up to education to provide a cure for poverty, ignorance, mental deficiency, joblessness, bad governance, poor communication system, hunger, inadequate shelter among other socio-economic problems.

Occupational aspirations are defined as the statement of desired occupational goal given ideal conditions. Occupational aspirations represent an individual orientation towards a desired occupational goal under ideal conditions. More simply stated occupational aspirations provide information about an individual's interests (Hewitt, 2010). Occupational aspiration is literally defined as the desire to achieve a particular occupation. In this study, occupational aspiration describes person's desired occupational aim.

Students especially those with disabilities seem to be ignorant about the occupation to which they aspire. Because of this problem of ignorance, which some are facing, it is difficult to plan and make occupational aspirations (Karacay, 2015). Some students aspire to do certain things because of some basic needs, whether these needs are real or imagined. In essence, one who does not have a need for a particular thing does not worry about such a thing. The researcher also observed that some students engage in some occupations, because they feel they lack something which if present would give them satisfaction in an anticipated direction, and the something they feel they lack may be in terms of material wealth such as money or influence, prestige and recognition. Occupational needs arise when an individual encounters difficulties engaging in their occupations of daily living. Operationally, occupational needs are skills students need to acquire to get into desired occupations or to achieve their occupational aspiration

The psychological factors considered in this study are decision making ability, problem solving skill, and self-concepts vis-à-vis occupational aspiration of students with disabilities in Southwest, Nigeria. Decision making is defined as the assessment of two or more options and the ability to choose between them. The decision-making process is a cognitive process that entails choosing the appropriate behaviour with a tendency (preference) to satisfy a need as soon as it arises and to eliminate accompanying tension (Budak, 2000). Luzzo, Hitchings, Retish, and Shoemaker (1999) found out that students with disabilities tend to display attitudes and beliefs about occupational decision-making that kept them from getting the most out of occupational development. They noted that these individuals felt as if they had little control over the decision-making situation and low confidence in their ability to affect and make decisions about their future occupations.

It appears that students with disabilities lack social and academic skills and as a result, they may exhibit low occupational decision-making skills. They might not learn the necessary skills to promote effective occupational decision-making skills. It is important for students with disabilities to obtain decision making skills in order to assist them with the occupational development and exploration process as well as helping them to determine their need for specific occupational accommodations.

Problem solving ability seems to be the result of thinking ability with efficiency of thought shown in the form of ability to solve the problem. It may be said that problem solving ability is the next step to reasoning skills. Lack of problem solving capability could affect students with disabilities. It has been observed that students with disability depend largely on their teachers, parents and even colleagues in order to find solution to their immediate

problems including school works (Agran & Wehmeyer, 2014). Problem solving skill is very significant in occupational aspiration decision making.

Problem solving is a skill and that the absence of this skill, which is related to limited opportunities for learning and poor socialization, can result in poor mental health and behavioural problems. Even though it has been noted that problem solving is a necessary skill for occupational development and exploration, Agran and Wehmeyer (2014) found that there are low expectations for student with intellectual and developmental disabilities to learn and develop strong problem solving skills. During adolescence, individuals become more autonomous and are expected to handle more complex problems on their own at a more frequent rate and because this is such an important part of occupational development and exploration and because studies have shown that individuals with disabilities lack this skill, it is important to note how this skill could be affected by disability and other psychosocial factors.

Research has shown that academic self-concepts have a significant impact on students' occupational aspirations, this is the major reason educators need to investigate students' academic self-concept so as to be able to foster learning in schools and improve their performance in choosing an occupation. Self-concept describes the totality of the individual's thoughts and feelings having reference to himself as a person.

According to Woolfolk (2006), self-concept is an agent of self-development especially among children. A child's development can be observed as they grow since each child is a unique person. As such, co-operation from different parties is required to ensure the development of a positive self-concept in a child. In a research, Hussien and Al-Qaryouti (2015) relates self-concept to self-assessment or self-perception. The concept largely represents the extent of an individual's faith in his/her own characteristics. This concept also reflects a person's judgment of himself based on the way he/she weigh the importance of success. Some students with disabilities could have lower confidence about themselves in relation to occupational aspiration.

This study explored psychological determinants of occupational aspiration among students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. the psychological determinants of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in secondary schools;
- ii. the relationship between decision making ability and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities;
- iii. the relationship between problem solving skill and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities; and
- iv. the relationship between self-concept and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

Research Question

This research question was raised to guide the study:

1. What are the psychological determinants of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in secondary schools in South-west, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between decision making ability and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

2. There is no significant relationship between problem solving skill and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.
3. There is no significant relationship between self-concept and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities

Methodology

The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population consisted of all 1,106 students with disabilities in integrated public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria (Source: States Ministry of Education, 2020). The sample for this study consisted of 349 students with disabilities from 12 integrated public secondary schools in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

An instrument tagged "Psychological Determinants and Occupational Aspiration Questionnaire (PDOAQ)" was used to collect relevant data for the study from the respondents. PDOAQ consisted of three sections namely section A, B and C. *Section A* of the PDOAQ sought for information on demography about the respondents. *Section B* consisted of 12 items on psychological factors as it relates to occupational aspiration while *Section C* consisted of 20 items on occupational aspiration.

The face and content validity of the instruments were determined by Guidance and Counselling experts and experts in Tests and Measurement. The instrument was said to have facial relevance and concerned with the subject matter, they claimed to measure. The reliability of the instrument was determined through test re-test method. A co-efficient of 0.81 was gotten and this was considered high enough to make the instrument reliable and useful for the study. The responses obtained were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics, while the hypotheses postulated were subjected to inferential statistics of Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the psychological determinants of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in secondary schools in South-west, Nigeria?

In answering this question, data on psychological factors were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of PDOAQ (item 1 – 12) in the questionnaire. The data were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation. In table 1, the mean cut-off mark of 2.50 was derived by finding the average of the scoring system. Mean score of items greater than mean cut-off of 2.50 were accepted while those less than 2.50 were rejected.

Table 1: Mean Scores of psychological determinants of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities

S/N	ITEMS	Agreed (%)	Disagreed (%)	Mean
1	Decision Making Ability	272 (77.9)	77 (22.1)	2.94
2	Problem Solving Skill	286 (81.9)	63 (18.1)	2.87
3	Self – Concept	299 (85.7)	50 (14.3)	2.99

Mean Cut-off: 2.50

Figure i: Bar chart showing the psychological determinants of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities

Table 1 and figure i showed the psychological determinants of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in secondary schools in South-west, Nigeria. Using the criterion mean score of 2.50 as cut-off to determine the affirmative of each statement, the respondents indicated that the average mean mark of decision making ($\bar{x} = 2.94$), problem solving skill ($\bar{x} = 2.87$) and self-concept ($\bar{x} = 2.99$). It is deduced from the above that the psychological determinants of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities are decision making, problem solving skill and self-concept.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between decision making ability and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

In testing this hypothesis, data on decision making sub-variable of psychosocial factors were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of PDOAQ (item 1 – 4) in the questionnaire. Data on occupational aspiration were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of PDOAQ (item 1 – 20) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between decision making ability and occupational aspirations

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Decision Making Ability	349	11.75	1.72	0.534*	0.000
Occupational Aspirations	349	40.52	7.88		

*P<0.05

Table 2 showed that the r-cal value of 0.534 was significant at 0.05 level of significant because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between decision making ability and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities. Decision making ability is moderately and positively related to occupational aspirations.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between problem solving skill and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

In testing this hypothesis, data on problem solving skill sub-variable of psychosocial factors were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of PDOAQ (item 5 – 8) in the questionnaire. Data on occupational aspiration were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of PDOAQ (item 1 – 20) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 3.

Table 3: Relationship between problem solving skill and occupational aspirations

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Problem Solving Skill	349	11.48	1.10	0.099	0.066
Occupational Aspirations	349	40.52	7.88		

P>0.05

Table 3 showed that the r-cal value of 0.099 is not significant at 0.05 level of significant because the P-value (0.066) > 0.05. The null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that there is no significant relationship between problem solving skill and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between self-concept and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities.

In testing this hypothesis, data on self-concept sub-variable of psychosocial factors were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of PDOAQ (item 9 – 12) in the questionnaire. Data on occupational aspiration were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section C of PDOAQ (item 1 – 20) in the questionnaire. Both were compared for statistical significance using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 levels. The result is presented in table 4.

Table 4: Relationship between self-concept and occupational aspirations

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Self-Concept	349	11.94	1.01	0.460*	0.000
Occupational Aspirations	349	40.52	7.88		

*P<0.05

Table 4 showed that the r-cal value of 0.460 was significant at 0.05 level of significant because the P-value (0.000) < 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there was significant relationship between self-concept and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities. Self-concept is moderately and positively related to occupational aspirations.

Discussion

The study revealed that the psychological determinants of occupational aspirations of students with disabilities are decision making, problem solving skill and self-concept. In line

with this finding, Ajuwon (2008) submitted that many complex variables impact on occupational aspirations; these include problem solving skill, self-concept and decision making.

It was further revealed that there was significant relationship between decision making ability and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities. This implies that decision making ability could determine the occupational aspiration of students with disabilities. The probable reason for this finding could be due to the fact that occupational aspiration involves the assessment of two or more options and the ability to choose between them. The researcher infers that choosing an occupation might be difficult for someone without ability to make decisions. In line with this finding, Lusk and Fazarro (2006) and Humes and Hohenshil (2004) concluded that a significant relationship existed between decision making ability and occupational aspirations.

The study however revealed that there was no significant relationship between problem solving skill and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities. This implies that problem solving skill has no link with occupational aspiration of students with disabilities. The finding however contradicted the submission of Osoro (2012) who concluded that lack of problem solving skill during secondary school negatively affected their occupational aspirations.

In addition, the study revealed that there was significant relationship between self-concept and occupational aspirations of integrated secondary school students with disabilities. This implies that self-concept could determine the occupational aspiration of students with disabilities. The probable reason for this finding could be because the totality of the individual's thoughts and feelings might go a long way to determine occupational interest. In line with this finding, Evans (2008) concluded that self-concept influenced occupational aspiration of students with disabilities

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that decision-making ability and self-concept are related to occupational aspirations of students with disabilities in integrated secondary schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Parents in collaboration with school management should make available necessary support that could aid students with disabilities in making the right decision about occupational aspiration.
2. The government should provide necessary facilities that will help students with disabilities have confidence in their abilities and individual's faith in his/her own characteristics.

References

- Agran, M., & Wehmeyer, M. (2014). *Teaching problem solving to students with mental retardation*. Washington, DC: American Association on Mental Retardation.
- Budak, S. (2000). Decision making styles East and West: Is it time to move beyond cross-cultural research. *International Journal of Sociology and Anthropology*, 3(12), 452-459.
- Evans, D. W. (2008). Development of self-concept in children with mental retardation: Organismic and contextual factors. In J. A. Burack, R. M. Hodapp, & E. Zigler (Eds.),

Handbook of mental retardation and development (pp. 462–480). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.

- Hewitt, J. (2010). Factors influencing Occupational aspiration. Retrieved on 25/04/2018 from www.ehow.com
- Humes, C. W., & Hohenshil, T. A. (2004). Occupational development and occupation education for handicapped students: A re-examination. *Occupational Guidance Quarterly*, 34, 31-40.
- Hussien, J.H. & Al-Qaryouti, I. (2015). General education teachers' perceived self-efficacy in teaching students with disabilities in Oman. Accessed from www.ajiebd.net on 22/4/20
- Karacay, N. (2015). Choice and Control New Opportunities for People with Developmental Disabilities. *Annals of Clinical Psychiatry*, 5(3), 151-161
- Lusk, S. L. & Fazarro, D. (2006). Effects of Psychosocial Factors on Occupation and workforce Development for Students with Disabilities. *Journal of Employment and Counselling*, 6(3), 316 – 325
- Luzzo, D.A., Hitchings, W.E., Retish, P., and Shoemaker, A., (1999). Evaluating differences in college students' occupational decision making on the basis of disability status. *Occupational development quarterly*, 48, 142-156.
- Olamide, J.U. & Olawaye, E.A. (2013), Deployment and use of assistive technology devices among special needs persons in Nigeria. *The Special Educator, journal publication of Nigeria Association of Special Education Teachers*, 8 (2), 80-94.
- Osoro, J. M. (2012). Integrated Education and Other Factors associated with Occupational aspirations Among Learners with Visual Impairments in Kenyan Public Universities. Nairobi: Unpublished.
- Woolfolk, K. (2006). Occupation education for students with visual impairments. *Review*, 28, 89-93.

Cite this article:

Author(s), OKE, CHIGOZIE CELESTINA, (2021). "Psychological Determinants of Occupational Aspiration Among Students with Disabilities in Integrated Secondary Schools in Southwest, Nigeria". **Name of the Journal:** International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 10- 20. **DOI:** <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5014810> , Special Issue: 6, Vol.: 3, Article: 1, Month: June, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

